

Influence of Supply Chain Management Processes on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties

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Abstract: There has been a rise in complaints by the public, professionals and other stakeholder's about the performance of Non-Governmental organizations in Kenya. This can be associated with supply chain management challenges. Non-Governmental Institutions in Kenya have for a long time been struggling with serious issues of poor supplier management where cases of misappropriation of funds have been reported because their current associations are based on trust and commitment which affects the delivery of services in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of the supply chain management. The specific objectives of the study were to assess the influence of logistic management and order fulfillment on the performance of Non-governmental organization in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties. The study was anchored on the concept of the contingency theory and the Bounded rationality theory of economics. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population was 84 officer in charge of procurement or store from 84 Non-governmental organization in Nakuru, town. Since the study population was small, a census design was adopted. Structured questionnaires were used to collect primary data from the respondents. Data collection process began by getting a formal letter from the university authorizing the field study. A pilot study was conducted in Eldoret town to establish the validity and reliability of the questionnaires. The study used SPSS Version 24 to analyze descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to show frequencies, percentages standard deviation and means while inferential statistics were used to show relationship between variables. The study revealed that a moderate positive correlation existed between logistic management and organization performance of NGO in Nakuru town ($r = 0.441$; $p < 0.05$). The study also revealed that a moderate positive correlation existed between order fulfillment and organization performance of NGO in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties ($r = 0.641$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that the organization has implemented aspects such as vision and mission of the strategy which improves the performance of supply chain process. The study also concluded that stockyard planning helps the organization to maximize the throughput without causing unacceptable delays during shipment of the stocks. The study recommended that Non-governmental organization should adopt demand forecasting because it allows the company to take several business decisions, such as planning the production process, purchasing raw materials, managing funds, and deciding the price of the product. The study recommended that a study should be conducted on the supplier selection criteria and performance of non-governmental organizations

Keywords: Order Fulfillment, Logistics Management, Non-governmental organization

I. INTRODUCTION

A supply chain is essentially a network consisting of suppliers, manufacturers, distributors, retailers and customers. The network supports three types of flows which require careful design and close coordination. The first is material flows, which represent physical product flows from suppliers to customers as well as reverse flows for product returns, servicing and recycling. The second is information flows, which represent order transmission and order tracking and which coordinate the physical flows. The third is financial flows, which represent credit terms, payment schedules and consignment arrangements (Kleindorfer & Van Wassenhove, 2016). Supply chain management (SCM) represents a significant change in the way that organizations view themselves and has witnessed values created through the

integration and coordination of supply, demand and relationships in order to satisfy customers in an effective and profitable manner both in the private and public sectors, (Walker & Wendy, 2016).

In Pakistan Pires (2014), observed that SCM process are linked to initiatives for changing the management of business processes in the supply chain. Further he argued that supply chain process are deliberated tangible activities or technologies that play a significant role in focal firm collaboration with its suppliers and customers. According to Pires (2014), through sustainable sourcing processes organizations can improve supplier disclosure and risk management capabilities and support information exchange and verification. Measuring supplier performance by addressing suppliers 'sustainability process drives improvement of internal and external standards and facilitates disclosure and transparency. This in turn supports compliance with any environmental regulation and enables the ability to better understand and minimize risks associated to specific products or suppliers. Procurement function credibility and collaborative supplier dialogue also favor the building of a sustainable supply chain that ultimately increases Pakistan's brand reputation and companies' value.

In South Africa, Lambert, (2016) observed that strengthening the management of supply chain of organization is seen to enhance customer satisfaction and to improve the performance of the organization. When offering relief to disaster victims, Humanitarian organizations supply chain plays a significant role which includes, planning and management of all events involved with sourcing ,procurement and all logistic management activities, it also comprises collaboration and coordination with actors who can be suppliers, donors, intermediaries, beneficiaries , third party service providers , developmental programs and operational activities in times of disaster and all the actors who are concerned with information, materials and financial flows of these programs, (Lambert, 2016). In Uganda Khalid (2012) found that technological integration emerges as the core supply chain management practices frequently identified and is contingent with a number of other practices. Further, supply chain management practices including long-term relationship development, partner development, joint development, enhanced communication, learning, stakeholder management and innovation have regularly been referred to and are considered important in improving the performance of public institutions.

In Kenya supply chain management activities, like the use of information technology and decision making structures, in addition to information sharing, collaboration and integration of stakeholders, have enabled many industries to improve their supply chain by reducing inefficiencies, improving service, and cutting operating costs. Nevertheless, despite the well documented evidence of significant competitive advantage and cost reduction resulting from supply chain management process little is known about determinants of effective implementation of these process in international humanitarian organizations in Kenya (McKone-Sweet, 2015). Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), like many other companies, are often faced with the challenge of managing their supply chains with dwindling financial resources, a lack of expertise, and insufficient personnel. Most of these organizations are surprised to learn that the use of best process in procurement processes can actually help them operate more efficiently while reducing their operating costs by as much as 60%.An efficient but flexible humanitarian relief supply chains is the key subject in disaster relief, discussed from academics as well as practitioners (Kováč & Spens, 2017).

In Kenya, Non-governmental organization (NGOs) in Kenya are licensed and regulated by the NGO Coordination Board. These organizations supplement government efforts to improve the living standards through implementation of diverse donor funded proposals, (Kirugu, 2015). The primary objective of Non-governmental / humanitarian organizations is to save lives, alleviate suffering and maintain human dignity during and in the aftermath of man-made crises and natural disasters, as well as to prevent and strengthen preparedness for the occurrence of such situations (Huber, 2014). There are many humanitarian organizations operating in the developing world, Kenya included. These organizations can be broadly divided into two categories: those that are purely originated and managed by Kenyans and those that are foreign in origin and control (Kariuki, 2015). There are a myriad of Non-Governmental organizations in Kenya with the collective obligation of striving to meet humanitarian needs. According to Kariuki, (2015) these organizations provide humanitarian assistance in ways that are supportive of recovery and long-term development, striving to ensure support, where appropriate, to the maintenance and return of sustainable livelihoods and transitions from humanitarian relief to recovery and development activities. A case in point on the important role played by humanitarian organizations was the assistance of the 2008 post-election violence (PEV) victims.

Statement of the Problem

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have played a major role in pushing for sustainable development both at the national and international level. However these organizations have experienced pressure when responding to emergencies in organized, timely, effective and appropriate manner. There has been a rise in complaints by the public, professionals and other stakeholder's about the performance of Non-Governmental organizations, (Kenya NGOs Coordination Board, 2019). This is associated with supply chain management challenges. Non- Governmental Institutions in Kenya have for a long time been struggling with serious issues of poor supplier management where cases of misappropriation of funds have been reported because their current associations are not based on trust and commitment which affects the delivery of services in terms a of efficiency and effectiveness of the supply chain management (World Bank, 2018). According to National Council of NGOs in Nakuru town, more than a quarter of registered NGOs have stopped their operations. Among the cited reasons is poor management of supply chain process. Several studies have been conducted on supply chain management, for instance; a study conducted by Kinyua (2013) on the Supply chain performance in humanitarian organizations in Kenya. Another study by Githeu (2014) on supply chain management process and performance of commercial banks in Kenya. Gerald, (2016) factors affecting the performance of supply chain financing in Kenya. Findings from these studies indicated that among characteristics of supply chain, relationships with supplier strategy has the maximum relationships with organizational performance of companies operation. However, very few studies have been conducted on the effect of supply chain management processes on the performance of Non-governmental organization. In response to the gaps identified there is the need to address them by conducting a study on factors influencing the supply chain management processes on the performance non-governmental organization in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

The general objective of the study was to assess the influence of supply chain management processes on performance of Non-Governmental Organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties .

Specific Objectives

- i. To determine the influence of logistic management performance of Non-governmental organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties
- ii. To establish the influence of order fulfillment on the performance of Non-governmental organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: Logistic management has no significant effect on the performance of Non-governmental organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties

H₀₂: Order fulfillment has no significant effect on the performance of Non-governmental organizations in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study was informed by the resource based view theory and the bounded rationality theory of economics.

Resource Based View Theory

This theory was developed by Penrose in 1959 and involves identification and analyzing business's management strategic advantages that are founded within the investigative and its different grouping of skills, assets, intangibles and capabilities as an organization. The basic principle of resource based view theory premise is that any given specific organization is fundamentally different from each other because each firm has a "unique" package of funds intangible and tangible resources and abilities of the organization so as to use of those resources. The resource based view theory emphasizes the firm's resources as the fundamental determinants of competitive advantage and performance. It adopts two assumptions in analyzing sources of competitive advantage (Peteraf & Barney, 2013). The resource-based method enables businesses with higher structures and systems being cost-effective especially because they involve themselves within the strategic investments that might discourage entries and raise the prices beyond long run costs. However, such firms have substantial lesser costs or even bid a markedly higher product or quality recital

Bounded Rationality Theory of Economics

The bounded rationality theory of economics was proposed by Simon, (1951). The theory assumes that an organizations recognize that individuals are subject to bounded rationality. This means that individuals are limited in their scope to act fully rationally because of limitations relating to both information at their disposal and their computational skills. Transactions can be characterized by an imbalance of information, so there is likely to be a dependency relationship between the parties involved. In particular, one party to the transaction often has either more information and/or better bargaining power than the other, (Zhenxin 2011) On this basis the theory identifies two types of parties to a transaction. The principal is a party who wishes to secure provision of some good or service but does not have the necessary specialized knowledge, skills or assets. The principal employs an agent to undertake this task and in the process delegates some control to that party (Grossman & Hart, 2013). The theory is relevance to the current study in that for organization to effectively implement supply chain processes partnership has to be done based on information sharing and logistics management that is effective through use of information systems in organization such as the NGOs.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON VARIABLES

Logistic Management

Logistics is an important component of supply chain management (Stank 2015). The Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (2017) defines logistics management as “that part of supply chain management that plans, implements, and controls the efficient, effective forward and reverse flow and storage of goods, services and related information between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customers’ requirements.” Both Stank and Lin (2016) describe the importance of integrating the logistics processes of all supply chain partners to better serve the needs of ultimate customers. Logistics management requires a comprehensive set of performance indicators that measure both tangible assets and intellectual capital (IC) of organizations. Nevertheless, most of the measures used in the past mainly related to the financial aspect, although some specific components of IC, such as process efficiency and effectiveness, have been considered, (Lambert & Burduroglu, 2015). In the current business environment, logistics is a vital managerial issue for all businesses, not only for manufacturing, or goods-oriented, industries but also for service-oriented industries (Chiu, 2016). Moreover, well executed logistics is empirically linked to enhanced organizational performance.

Logistics managers pay special attention to the records of the time required for procurement and retention according to each product. For each product in stock they should know the time needed for their purchase from order to delivery, the time each product spends in stock indirectly reduces the value of the product. There is a need for keeping products in stock is less possible. As long as the quantity of products in stock is lower, the inventory cost will be smaller, (Esper 2017). Logistics managers know how to properly choose the location of warehouses. Good location of the warehouse is

advantage and every transport can be handled more promptly. Although the so called "idle" is inevitable in every transport, companies are constantly seeking ways to reduce it through proper storage of products and therefore, increasing their lifespan, (Lynch 2014).

Logistics managers keeping electronic records of inventories facilitate inventory control and shorten the time required for ordering products (Storey, 2016). Detailed records kept for each executive transport in the company, facilitates the selection of any subsequent transport, comparing the cost of previous transports. The evidence of each transport shows the time required for delivery and the so called breakpoints. The future planning of any transport avoids all breakpoints that have occurred in previous transports. A detailed record of any transport should also be carried out in a special program or electronically. The existence of such systems and databases allows quick comparison of data from past activities and provides improved activity or reducing potential costs and time lost so the company can choose the most favorable and cheapest option (Bowersox 2016).

Logistics is termed as the part of supply chain management that is involved with flow of information, products and services (Stevenson, 2015). In a similar way, Kiraga (2014) offers the definition of logistics to be planning, implementation and control of procedures for effective supply chain management practices. While transportation on the other hand entails those methods and techniques that ensure timely and well-coordinated delivery of goods (Stock & Lambert, 2016). Through logistics and transportation, the operational performance is enhanced through reduced cost, reduced capital and improved service delivery (Onyango, 2011).

Order Fulfillment

Order fulfillment is the supply chain management process that balances the customers' requirements with the capabilities of the supply chain. With the right process in place, can match supply with demand proactively and execute the plan with minimal disruptions. The process is not limited to forecasting. It includes synchronizing supply and demand, increasing flexibility, and reducing variability, (Reno 2016). Duffy and Dale (2016) explained that order fulfillment (OF) is most important factor for business to consumer operations. Perfect order is an order delivered to a customer that is "complete, accurate, on time and in perfect condition". At the operational level, the order fulfillment process focuses on transactions and at strategic level, management can focus on making critical improvements to the process that influence the financial performance of the firms, its customers and its suppliers, (Hoffman 2015). Lambert (2014) observed order fulfillment is a supply chain process that involves more than just filling orders, it encompasses all activities essential to define customer requirements, design logistics network, and enable to a firm to meet customer orders until minimizing the total delivered cost.

The OF process should have strategic and operational management teams that include members that represent multiple functional areas and include members from supply chain partners if possible (Croxtan, 2016). "At the strategic level, the process team designs the operational OF process. This includes designing the network, establishing policies and procedures, and determining the role of technology in the process" (Croxtan, 2016). The OF process is also a vital factor in achieving customer satisfaction and presents an opportunity to improve operations and achieve a competitive advantage (Davis-Sramek, Germain, & Stank, 2016). "The shift has been to create a competitive advantage by successfully 'pushing the envelope' through leveraging the 'intangibles' in the firm's order fulfillment process, such as the ease of doing business, delivery dependability, and responsiveness to requests" (Davis-Sramek, Germain, & Stank, 2016). It must be noted that creating a competitive advantage through service offered and provided is only an advantage if the customer values the service and perceives it as a benefit

Order fulfillment and service quality is critical, not only in supply chain but also among service providers to be able to offer quality goods or services effectively and efficiently. Order fulfillment are short-term plans designed to implement the sales and operations plan. Often, several jobs must be processed at one or more workstation. (Froehle 2015) Order scheduling can loosely be defined as an act of defining priorities or arranging activities to meet certain requirements. It has two levels, macro level which include company-wide, factory-wide or those multinational companies. The other category is the micro level errands including; shop, work stations. Typically, a variety of tasks can be performed at each workstation. If schedules are not carefully planned bottlenecks and waiting lines may develop. When a job order is received for a part, the raw materials are collected and the batch is moved to its first operation. (Wolcott, 2016). The colored arrows show that jobs follow different routes through the manufacturing process, depending on the product being made. At each workstation, the next job to process is a decision because the arrival rate of jobs at a workstation often differs from the processing rate of the jobs at a workstation, thereby creating a waiting line (Sampson, 2016).

V. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Logistic Management

Mwangangi (2016) conducted a study on the influence of logistics management on performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. The study used both descriptive and explanatory research designs. The target population was the manufacturing firms registered by the Kenya National Bureau of Statistics as at 2010 and the respondents were the designated heads of logistics management of these firms. A semi-structured questionnaire was administered through the e-mail survey and hand delivery. Secondary data was obtained from both published and unpublished records. The findings of the study revealed that transport management; inventory management; order process management and information flow management were individually predictors of firm performance with inventory management being the most significant predictor. The study established that logistics information system was a moderating factor in the study.

Green (2017) conducted a study on the impact of logistics performance on organizational performance in a supply chain context. The aim of the study to assess a logistics performance model incorporating logistics performance as the focal construct with supply chain management strategy as antecedent and organizational performance, both marketing and financial, as consequences. Data from a national sample of 142 plant and operations managers are analyzed using a structural equation modeling methodology. The results indicate that logistics performance is positively impacted by supply chain management strategy and that both logistics performance and supply chain management strategy positively impact marketing performance, which in turn positively impacts financial performance. Neither supply chain management strategy nor logistics performance was found to directly impact financial performance.

Natasha, and Sasho (2017) conducted a study on the impact of logistics management practices on company's performance. To collect accurate data, the study adopted the use of questionnaire as a research tool. From 170 questionnaires distributed, 110 questionnaires were answered, from which 105 questionnaires were used for analysis. The analyzed data revealed that effectiveness in logistical management was not at a high level. Among the main reasons that influenced the effectiveness were inventory management and transportation of products. The slow inventory turnover of the companies in the supply chain brings obstacles, delays, products obtained not by expectations of consumers, etc. At the same time, problems in transportation of products bring deterioration effectively managing logistics operations

Order Fulfillment

Mishra (2017) sought to investigate the impact of perfect order fulfillment on quality level and SCM performance. The purpose of the study was to empirically test a conceptual framework based upon three constructs, perfect order fulfillment (POF), quality level (QL) performance, and supply chain management (SCM) performance. Various statistical techniques were used to verify, validate and test the reliability of the hypothesis and their sub dimensions. Results of structural modelling revealed that POF dimensions have a direct and significant impact towards enhancing QL and SCM performance. Also, QL performance shows a direct, positive impact on SCM performance.

Njeru (2014) sought to investigate the factors affecting effective order fulfillment and performance of procurement practices in tertiary public training institutions in Kenya. A descriptive correlational research design was adopted and the target population comprised 40 tertiary public training institutions in Kenya. Stratified random sampling technique was applied to select a sample size of 35 tertiary public training institutions. Questionnaires were used as the main data collection instruments and were pretested using a pilot study for validity and reliability. Descriptive and inferential statistics data analysis results revealed that the employed procurement policies, supplier management strategies, inventory management methods, professional training and use of ICT based systems hampered effective implementation of procurement practices in over 80% of tertiary public training institutions in Kenya. It was concluded that supplier management followed by training and then procurement policies are the major factors that mostly affect order fulfillment of procurement practices in tertiary public training institutions in Kenya.

Shahin (2016) sought to find out the effects of order fulfillment improvement by supplier relationship management with a case study in Pompaj Company. Specifically, the study sought to find out the effects of poor communication between the procurement department and suppliers and problems in procurement management. The study adopted Loop Diagram to find two main reasons for the performance of order scheduling. The study findings revealed that there might be many reasons in the order fulfillment delay, but focus can be placed on the first stage of a supply chain, which is related to suppliers and supplier relationship management (SRM).

Ogwang(2015) conducted study on the influence of order fulfillment on performance of Kisumu water and sewerage company limited, Kenya. The study was guided by game theory and resource-based theory. Survey research design was adopted. The study population comprised of the 128 procurement officers, middle level managers, supervisors and departmental heads. A sample of 57 respondents were derived from the aforesaid population using stratified random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used to facilitate in data collection. The findings of the study revealed that transparency in procurement was very important towards advancing the performance of the firm. The tendering process for the firm is advised to be open regardless of the magnitude of the goods and/or services intended to be procured.

Ndubi (2017) conducted a study on the effect of order fulfillment variability on inbound logistics performance in Safaricom limited. The target population was employees in Safaricom Limited who deal with the inbound logistics services and the sample frame was a register from Human resource department. The technique adopted in this research was Stratified sampling with a desired sample size of 70 respondents. Data collection was both quantitative and qualitative, questionnaires were used to collect data and analysis by use of linear regression model. The study found that production lead time, shipping lead time, customs brokerage turnaround time(TAT) and Receipt and inspection of goods velocity have a high impact on inbound logistics performance of the organization. The study concludes that lead time variability elements in production lead time; shipping lead time; customs brokerage turnaround time; receipt and inspection velocity have a significant effect on time delivery, cost and quality as a measure of inbound logistics performance

Research Gaps

Julian (2015) conducted a study on the relationship between strategic planning and organization's performance in non-governmental organizations (NGOS): a case of Action Aid, Kenya. Nonetheless, the study only targeted 17 respondents which implies that the issues in the study were not fully covered. The current study had a larger sample size of 84 respondents and was conducted in different NGOs thus coming up with a conclusive finding. Gitagia (2016) sought to investigate the practices and influence of strategic planning on the organizational performance of Kenyatta national hospital. Primary data was collected using interview guide. The researcher used content analysis to analyze the data through describing phenomena, however, the study used content analysis while the current adopted correlational and regression analysis. Nuahn (2017) conducted a study on the impact of supply planning and transportation process on performance of Kenya cooperative creameries. However, the study was conducted in manufacturing industry while the current study was conducted in non-governmental organization. Green (2017) conducted a study on the impact of logistics performance on organizational performance in a supply chain context. However, the study focused on the logistic management and left out other components of supply chain practices like the order fulfillment and planning which were included in the current study.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The descriptive research design describes the present status of a phenomenon, determining the nature of prevailing conditions, process, attitudes and seeks accurate descriptions (Mugenda, 2003). The descriptive study describes the phenomenon as it is on the ground without any manipulation of variables.

Target Population

The target population was 84 officers in charge of procurement or store from 84 Non-governmental organizations in Nakuru, town East and West Sub-Counties. Since the study population was small census design was adopted. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2012) a census design is a study of every unit, everyone or everything in a population. Census design increases reliability because there is no point of sampling allowing all the respondents to participate in the study.

Data Collection Instruments

Primary data was sourced from the respondents through the use of structured questionnaires. There are several advantages associated with the use of questionnaire and interviews schedule and which informs its usage in this study.

These advantages include ease of distribution and data collection, ease of data analysis. Research questionnaire were important in collecting more relevant information in relation to the stated objectives.

Data Collection Procedure

Data collection process began by getting a formal letter from the university authorizing the field study. The letter together with the consent statement was then presented to the respective NGOs as a means of seeking authority to collect data from the institution. The researcher also sought a permit from the national commission for science, technology and innovation (NACOSTI). Data was collected using drop and pick later method which was collected after two weeks

Pilot Testing

A pilot study was conducted in Eldoret town where 8 questionnaires were issued to the logistic and procurement managers operating with Non-governmental organization within Eldoret town.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The validity of this study was enhanced in search of views of experts in the field of study especially with the research supervisor. According to Cooper and Schindler (2011), pre-testing is a good way to eliminate the probability of face validity. Reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha. Items with reliability coefficients of at least 0.70 were accepted as valid and reliable in this research.

Data Analysis and Presentation

The study used SPSS Version 24 to analyze descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics was used to show frequencies, percentages standard deviation and means while inferential statistics were used to show relationship between variables. Pearson correlation coefficient was determined in the analysis and it enables the establishment of how the independent and dependent variables related to each other. Pearson correlation(r) establishes if there is a repetitious connection amongst the variables where the Pearson's correlation differs from +1 to -1, with 0 showing there lacks a relationship and 1 showing there is a perfect connection.

VII. FINDINGS

Response Rate

The study sample size of 84 respondents out of which 70 filled and returned the questionnaires giving a response rate of 83%. Two questionnaires were not obtained from the respondents 4 % response failure. With a 96% response rate, the study had a considerable sample size adequate for the research. According to Barbie (2014), a high response rate is advantageous since it greatly reduces non-response bias as compared to a low response rate

Demographic Information

Table 4.1: Age of the respondents

Age of the respondents	Frequency	Percentage
20-25 years	12	17
26-30 years	18	26
31-35 years	15	21
Above 35 years	25	36
Total	70	100

From the findings, 17% of the respondents indicated that they were in the age bracket of 20-25years, 26% indicated that they were in the age bracket of 26-30years, 21% indicated that they wer in the age bracket of 31-35years while 36% ndicated that they were above 35years. this implies that most of the respondents were above 30years. Age determines the efficiency of the procurement officers in the NGOs. Human resource above 35 years have been in the market for a while thus the undesrtand the procurement processes better than the youngsters.

Table 4.2: Respondents' Highest Level of Education

Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage
Professional Certificate	0	0
Post Graduate	22	31
Bachelors Degree	40	57
Diploma	8	12
Total	70	100

From the findings, 31% of the respondents indicated that they had attained post graduate education , 57% indicated that they had attained bachelors degree education while 12% indicated that they had attained diploma education This shows that majority of the respondents had attained bachelors degree education. The education level determines the efficiency of procurement officer. Officer with high education level tend to perform better.

Table 4.3: Duration of working in the Non-Governmental Organization.

Duration of Service	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 Years	0	0
1-5 Years	10	14
6-10 Years	15	21
More than 10 years	45	65
Total	70	100

According to the findings, 14% of the respondents indicated that they had been working in the NGOs for 1-5 years, 21% of the respondents indicated that they had been working in the NGOs for 6-10 years, while 65% of the respondents indicated that they had been working in the NGOs for more than 10 years. This shows that majority of the respondents had been working in the NGOs for more than 10 years. The duration of service an individual has worked determines his/her capacity. Employees who have longer working experience tend to have better skills.

Descriptive Findings and Discussions

Logistic Management

Table 4.4: Logistic Management on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

Logistic Management	S	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std
	%	%	%	%	%		
The organization does its transport network and route planning in consultation with the various stakeholders	37	34	10	16	3	3.855	1.185
The organization considers the ideal location of the warehouse to minimize the cost and time in distribution of goods	55	34	8	3	0	4.403	0.778
The organization ensures effective packaging which result to reduction of breakages and damages of goods	44	46	7	3	0	4.307	0.738
Management of returns is effectively done to avoid environmental degradation.	48	48	2	2	0	4.26	0.231
The firm adopts best process in the industry such as JIT and efficient demand response to prevent inventory build up	52	38	8	2	0	4.28	0.534
The organization have a constant communication with suppliers which help in the management of inventory level	49	31	14	6	0	4.62	0.323
The organization regularly check the inventory level to avoid over stocking	51	44	1	4	0	4.40	0.764

According to the findings majority of the respondents (71%) agreed that the organization does its transport network and route planning in consultation with the various stakeholders with a mean of 3.855 and an Std of 1.185. Majority of the respondents (89%) also agreed that the organization considers the ideal location of the warehouse to minimize the cost and time in distribution of goods with a mean of 4.403 and an Std of 0.778. The findings are in line with Komba, (2013) who noted that choosing the right warehouse location can make all the difference in how effective, efficient, and profitable a company is. Leasing or purchasing a warehouse is a major decision, and a choosing the right location can significantly enhance a company's ability to compete and effectively serve customers.

They further agreed (90%) that the organization ensures effective packaging which result to reduction of breakages and damages of goods with a mean of 4.307 and an Std of 0.738. The study findings concurs with Mumbi, (2016) who noted that the primary purpose of product packaging is to protect the product from damage. Product packaging not only protects the product during transit from the manufacturer to the retailer, but it also prevents damage while the product sits on retail shelves.

In addition majority of the respondents (96%) agreed that management of returns is effectively done to avoid environmental degradation with a mean of 4.26 and an Std of 0.231. Majority of the respondents (90%) also agreed that the organization adopts best process in the industry such as JIT and efficient demand response to prevent inventory buildup with a mean 4.28 and an Std of 0.534. Majority of them (80%) also agreed that the organization have a constant communication with suppliers which help in the management of inventory level with a mean of 4.62 and an Std of 0.323. Finally the majority of the respondents (95%) agreed that the organization regularly check the inventory level to avoid over stocking with a mean of 4.40 and an Std of 0.764. The findings concurs with, Nana, (2016) study which observed that efficient stock control allows you to have the right amount of stock in the right place at the right time. It ensures that capital is not tied up unnecessarily, and protects production if problems arise with the supply chain.

Order Fulfillment

Table 4.5: Order Fulfillment on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

Order Fulfillment	S	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std
	%	%	%	%	%		
The organization uses electronic order processing systems which reduces the order processing cost	60	16	12	9	0	4.32	0.472
The organization uses order tracking system which reduces the order processing time	51	44	1	4	0	4.42	0.745
The organization assesses the appropriate reorder level which ensures there's availability of adequate stock at all	58	24	8	4	6	4.18	0.912
The organization has a delivery schedule with ensures there smooth flow of products	40	48	4	8	0	3.98	1.032

According to the findings majority of the respondents (76%) agreed that the organization uses electronic order processing systems which reduces the order processing cost with a mean of 4.32 and an Std of 0.472. According to Sampson (2015) order processing software reduces the costs for manually transfer information from sales sheets and order forms into QuickBooks and the warehouse management software. Automatic integration between quality order processing software and the organization QuickBooks account reduces the time necessary for manual entry and also reduces the need for management controls to check the manual data entry.

Majority of the respondents (95%) also agreed that the organization uses order tracking system which reduces the order processing time with a mean of 4.42 and an Std of 0.745. Majority of the respondents also (82%) agreed that the organization assesses the appropriate reorder level which ensures there's availability of adequate stock at all with a mean of 4.18 and an Std of 0.912. The findings concurs with Deglin, (2015) who noted order management software brings all of the orders tracking in one location to process them from start to finish. This implies cutting down upon manual and time-killing mistakes. Eliminate every chance of manual inefficiencies with end-to-end process automation

In addition majority of the respondents (88%) agreed that the organization has a delivery schedule with ensures there smooth flow of products with a mean of 3.98 and an Std of 1.032. The study agree with a study with Jordan, (2014) study which noted that delivery schedule is one of the most commonly known procurement key performance indicators. It measures the timeliness of deliveries by suppliers against agreed requirement dates. The delivery schedules is typically used as a barometer of supplier health to ensure that they are doing as required.

Table 4.6 Performance of Non-Governmental Organization

Performance	S A %	A %	U %	D %	SD %	Mean	Std
The organization is able to meet its goals and objectives	50	34	8	4	4	4.15	0.921
The organization is able to meet its organization financial obligations	54	36	2	5	3	4.56	0.608
The organization is able to reach out to all its beneficiaries	48	40	3	5	4	4.13	0.513
The organization is able to retain its staffs because of the services offered.	63	32	0	3	2	4.60	0.670
The organization is able to deliver services to the beneficiaries as scheduled.	68	23	2	4	3	4.23	0.886

According to the findings majority of the respondents (84%) agreed that the organization is able to meet its goals and objectives with a mean of 4.15. Majority of the respondents (90%) also agreed that the organization is able to meet its organization financial obligations with a mean of 4.56. They further agreed (88%) that the organization is able to reach out to all its beneficiaries with a mean of 4.13. In addition majority of the respondents (95%) agreed that the organization is able to retain its staffs because of the services offered with a mean of 4.60. Finally, majority of the respondents (91%) agreed that the organization is able to deliver services to the beneficiaries as scheduled with a mean 4.23. The standard deviation ranged from 0.607 to 1.185 indicating that majority of the respondents agreed with the issues raised.

Test for Multicollinearity

A multicollinearity test was carried out to ensure that the independent variables did not have co-linearity amongst themselves. The variance inflation factors (VIF) and Tolerance were used to assess multicollinearity. The VIF, which stands for variance inflation factor, is (1 / tolerance) and as a rule of thumb, a variable whose VIF value is greater than 10 may merit further investigation.

Table 4. 7: Tolerance and VIF Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Logistic Management	.657	1.671
Order Fulfillment	.815	1.455

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Non-governmental organizations

From the findings, the variable logistic management had a tolerance of 0.657 and a VIF of 1.671, order fulfillment had a tolerance of 0.815 and a VIF of 1.455. Since the tolerance for all the variables was more than 0.1 and the VIF was not more than 10 therefore there was no need of further investigations.

Logistic Management on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

The study further examined the correlation between logistic management on organization performance of NGOs in Nakuru town, Kenya. The results of correlation analysis are outlined in Table 4.8.

Table 4. 8: Logistic Management on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

		Organization Performance of NGOs
Logistic Management	Pearson Correlation	.441*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024
	N	70

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The study as shown in Table 4.8 established that a moderate positive correlation existed between logistic management and organization performance of NGO in Nakuru town ($r = 0.441$; $p < 0.05$). The results of the correlation analysis indicated that better logistic management improve the organization performance of NGO in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties The findings is in agreement with, Mugeru, (2014) study which noted logistic management reduces risk related to business activities and helps it to take efficient decisions. The importance of logistic management is to increase more supplies a goods which helps a firm in better planning related to business goals which has a positive effect on organization performance.

Order Fulfillment on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

The study further examined the correlation between order fulfillments and organization performance of NGOs in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties. The results of correlation analysis are outlined in Table 4.9.

Table 4. 9: Order Fulfillment on Performance of Non-Governmental Organizations

		Organization Performance of NGOs
Order Fulfillment	Pearson Correlation	.641*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.031
	N	70

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The study as shown in Table 4.9 established that there was a moderate positive correlation existed between order fulfillment and organization performance of NGO in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties ($r = 0.641$; $p < 0.05$). The results of the correlation analysis indicated that better order fulfillment improve the organization performance of NGO in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties The findings is in agreement with Mauyo,(2013) study which found that having a well outlined and smooth order fulfillment process will help the business continue to draw customers and satisfy them with the products delivered. This model builds a product against a sales forecast, and sells to the customer from the finished goods stock.

Table 4.10: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
	(Constant)	1.082	.127	8.529	.000
1	Logistic Management	.159	.042	.220	.023
	Order fulfillment	.313	.033	.432	.015

Table 4.10 shows the overall significant test results for the hypothesized research model. The interpretations of the findings indicated follow the following regression model.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

Therefore,

$$Y = 1.082 + 0.159 X_1 + 0.313 X_2 + \varepsilon$$

According to the intercept (β_0), when the three independent variables are held constant, the value of organization performance of the NGOs will be 1.082. Holding all the other variables constant, a unit increase in logistic management would lead to a 0.159 improvement in organization performance of the NGOs in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties. Further holding on the other independent variables constant, a unit increase in order fulfillment would lead to a 0.313 improvement in organization performance of the NGOs Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties.

Hypothesis Testing

The study sought to test the hypothesis that: H02: There is no significant influence of logistic management on organization performance of NGOs in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties. From the findings the p-value was 0.023 which was less than the 0.05 significant level. Therefore, based on the rule of significance, the study rejects the null hypothesis (H02) and concluded that logistic management has a significant influence on organization performance in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties.

The study sought to test the hypothesis that: H03: There is no significant influence of order fulfillment on organization performance of NGOs in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties. From the findings the p-value was 0.015 which was less than the 0.05 significant level. Therefore, based on the rule of significance, the study rejects the null hypothesis (H03) and concluded that order fulfillment has a significant influence on organization performance of NGOs in Nakuru Town East and West Sub-Counties.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Basing on the findings on the effects of logistic management, the study concluded that the organization adopts best process in the industry such as JIT and efficient demand response to prevent inventory buildup. Moreover, the study concluded that the organization have a constant communication with suppliers which help in the management of inventory level. In addition the study also concluded that the organization regularly check the inventory level to avoid over stocking.

The study concluded that the organization has integrated order scheduling processes which reduces the lag time between the supply chain orders thus improving supply chain performance. Stockyard planning helps the organization to maximize the throughput without causing unacceptable delays during shipment of the stocks. The study also concluded that the organization reviews the inventory level which reduces cases of stock out.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study recommended that the Non-governmental organization should adopt logistic management because good logistics management helps businesses deliver better service to their customers. Correct management of the company's logistics should make the company strive to improve delivery times and offer better customer service to all those who use the products. Dealing directly with the client gives the organization an advantage over competitor. The study also recommended that the NGOs should adopt order fulfillment because it is the customers' orders that put the supply chain in motion, and filling them efficiently and effectively is the first step in providing customer service.

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